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ULOGA SINDIKATA U INKLUZIJU RADNIKA

U radu se analizira uloga sindikata u postupku inkluzije ranjivih skupina radnika. Glavni fokus bit će stavljen na različite instrumente inkluzije nastale u okviru kolektivnog pregovaranja na razini poduzeća ili višoj razini, kao i nove instrumente inkluzije (primjerice partnerstva s drugim socijalnim akterima). Kolektivno pregovaranje omogućava inkluzivnu zaštitu najranjivijih skupina radnika, primjerice radnika migranata, radnika zaposlenih na temelju privremenih ugovora te drugih skupina ranjivih (nestandardnih) radnika. S druge strane, uloga radničkih predstavnika kod poslodavca može biti ključna u pružanju zaštite pojedinačnom radniku koji trpi diskriminaciju. Tradicionalno, snaga sindikata leži u zaštiti općih, kolektivnih interesa radnika, a rjeđe se sindikati bave nepovoljnim okolnostima (uvjetima rada) određenih skupina radnika. U radu se analiziraju učinkoviti instrumenti inkluzije, tj. odgovori na diskriminaciju, kao i konflikt koji se javlja između potreba određenog radnika (skupina radnika), s jedne, te potreba zajednice radnika, koje predstavlja sindikat, s druge strane.

Ključne reči: sindikat, inkluzija, ranjive skupine radnika.

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The Role of Trade Unions in Workers' Inclusion

The paper deals with the role of trade unions in the inclusion of vulnerable categories of workers. The main part will focus on different instruments of inclusion developed via collective bargaining agreements in general or at the company level, as well as new instruments of inclusion (e.g., partnerships with other social actors). As a model of co-regulation, collective bargaining enables inclusive labour protection, *inter alia*, through the coverage of enterprises and workers, for example migrant workers, workers employed based on temporary contracts and other categories of vulnerable (precarious, non-standard) workers. On the other hand, the role of the workers' representatives can be crucial in offering on-site remedy for an individual worker who suffered discrimination. Traditionally, the union's strength lies in the representation of common collective interests, while they seldom deal with the unfavourable circumstances (disadvantaged working conditions) of certain groups of workers and the differences among trade union members. The paper analyzes the most efficient instruments for inclusion and responses to discrimination, focusing on the role of the workers' representatives and the conflict between individual worker's needs, on the one hand, and the need of the 'community' of workers represented by trade union, on the other hand.

Keywords: trade union, inclusion, vulnerable workers.